

INFLUENCE OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON ANAEROBIC POWER AMONG HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on anaerobic power among hockey players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, thirty hockey players from Tamilnadu Physical Education and Sports University, Chennai were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years. The subjects were divided into two equal groups at random. The subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen players each. Group I acted as Experimental Group (yogic practices) and Group II acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses. The experimental group had achieved significant improvement on anaerobic power than the control group.

Key Words: Yogic practices, Speed, Balance, Hockey

Introduction:

Yoga provides one of the best means of self-improvement and attaining one's full potential. In the advanced stages of yoga, superconscious states are attained which result in a feeling of bliss, deep peace and the emergence of psychic powers. Yoga was developed and perfected over the centuries by philosophers and mystics in India. It is basically a method by which we increase the body's supply of energy and remove any interference to the transmission of energy throughout the body. Yoga has specialized in this subject for thousands of years, and streamlined the methods to attain this aim. These days, yoga classes are being held at almost health and wellness centers across the United States. Along with meditation, it is probably one of the most popular alternative therapy. Many physicians, who are skeptical about the efficacy of alternative medicine, support yoga with a passion. There are many clinical studies that show the effectiveness of yoga. And the best part of, it is something that can be done in the comfort of your home. A few breathing exercises recommended by yoga will go a long way towards better health and relaxation (Harinath et al. 2004).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on anaerobic power among hockey players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, thirty hockey players from Tamilnadu Physical Education and Sports University, Chennai were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years. The subjects were divided into two equal groups at random. The subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen players each. Group I acted as Experimental Group (yogic practices) and Group II acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Anaerobic Power of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	1201.86	1194.60	BG	396.03	1	396.03	0.05
			WG	197821.33	28	7065.04	
Post Test Mean	1429.60	1208.86	BG	365424.03	1	365424.03	95.77*
			WG	106837.33	28	3815.61	
Adjusted Post Mean	1429.94	1208.52	BG	366973.45	1	366973.45	94.31*
			WG	105060.04	27	3891.11	

* Significant at 0.05 level, Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20, 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of anaerobic power of experimental and control groups were 1429.94 and 1208.52 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 94.31 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on anaerobic power. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups differ significantly.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Anaerobic Power of Experimental Group and Control Groups

Conclusion:

The experimental group had achieved significant improvement on anaerobic power than the control group.

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